

7.6, 1.2% organic C, 44 kg available P/ha, and 313 kg available K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design.

One-half the PU was applied at transplanting and one-half equally divided into two topdressings at tillering and panicle initiation. NCU, LCU, and DCU were applied one-half at

transplanting and one-half at tillering. USG was placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills 1 wk after transplanting. All plots received 17.4 kg P and 33.3 kg K/ha. Two seedlings per hill of rice variety Jaya were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The field was flooded (5 cm ± 3 cm) by rain or irrigation from

transplanting to milk stage.

N levels and N sources significantly influenced yield (see table). All amended N fertilizers except DCU in 1983 performed better than PU in both years. USG outyielded other N sources, with 28% higher yield than PU in 1983 and 27.5% higher in 1984. □

Effect of transplanting date and N application on yield

M.S. Maskina, Bijay-Singh, and Yadvinder-Singh, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Under optimal water and minerals, applied N absorption by rice and its translation into grain yield are limited by such climatic factors as light and temperature. Transplanting date and crop duration seem to be important. We studied yield response to applied N at different transplanting dates.

The experiment was in a Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.5, 0.24% organic C, and 0.03% total N. Four levels of N (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha) were used in a split-plot design. PR106 seedlings at 45 d were transplanted on 9 Jun, 30 Jun, and 21 Jul at 15- × 15-cm spacing. Field plots were submerged 2 d before the

transplanting. Crop durations were 121, 112, and 101 d.

Although response to applied N was significant, transplanting date had a pronounced effect on the nature and extent of the response (see figure). Rice transplanted 9 Jun and 30 Jun and harvested at 121 and 112 d exhibited quadratic response curves that were almost flat with 180 kg N/ha. Rice transplanted 21 Jul matured in only 101 d and responded linearly, with lower yields than the crops transplanted in Jun, at least up to 180 kg N/ha. The influence of transplanting date and N was reflected primarily in tiller density and spikelet number.

The interaction between N level and date of transplanting was significant. Yield similar to those with 180 kg N/ha and 21 Jul transplanting could be obtained with 120 kg N/ha and 30 Jun transplanting or 60 kg N/ha and 9 Jun transplanting. □

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on lowland rice

B.K. Jena, P.K. Mahapatra, and G.K. Patro, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, India

We studied five sources of N during the 1984 wet season (WS) in a split-plot design with three replications. N levels were in the main plots and sources in the subplots. The soil was lateritic and sandy loam, pH 5.8, EC 0.112 dS/m, 0.73% organic C, 0.07% total N, 20 kg available P, and 140 kg available K/ha. Rice varieties were Lalat (135 d) during the WS and Jajati (120 d) during the dry season (DS). Spacing was 15 × 10 cm.

All N sources were applied in a single dose at transplanting except for prilled urea, which was split-applied: 25% at transplanting, 50% at tillering, and 25%

Effect of N source on yield and BB intensity. Bhubaneswar, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		BB ^a	
	WS	DS	WS	DS
N level				
No N	1.9	2.2	2	2
56 kg/ha	2.9	2.7	3	2
84 kg/ha	3.0	2.8	4	3
112 kg/ha	3.3	2.7	4	3
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.3	-	-
CV (%)	45	-	-	-
Source				
Prilled urea split application	3.0	2.5	3	2
Urea gypsum	3.0	2.8	3	2
Rock phosphate-coated urea	3.0	2.6	3	2
Urea supergranule	3.3	2.9	4	2
Urea nitro-humic acid	3.0	2.8	3	2
CD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	-	-
CV (%)	6	6	-	-

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale.

Effect of transplanting date on lowland rice response to N. Ludhiana, India.

at panicle initiation. The WS crop received 17 kg P and 33 kg K/ha.

All the treatments received 50-22-42 kg NPK/ha during the DS to study residual effects of N.

All N levels were superior to the control during both seasons (see table).

N at 56 kg/ha equaled 84 kg N/ha; 112 kg N/ha was best during the WS. USG gave the highest yields, 3.3 t/ha in the WS and 2.9 t/ha in the DS. DS yield was low because of a hailstorm at harvest. Residual effect was pronounced

with N levels as well as sources during DS.

Bacterial blight (BB) intensity increased with increasing N, and was higher in the WS than in the DS with respect to levels as well as sources. □

Constraints to rice yields in Punjab, Pakistan

M.S. Zia, M. Ashraf, and M. Munsif, Pakistan Agricultural Research Council, National Agricultural Research Centre, Soil Science Section, P. O., N.I. H., Park Road, Islamabad, Pakistan

We analyzed the contribution of various factors to the gap between potential and actual yields in farmers' field trials. The recommended inputs were land preparation by 2 plowings in dry soil and 4 plowings and 2 plankings in standing water, transplanting with 30-d-old seedlings, fertilizer at 110-26 kg NP/ha, plant density of 250,000 hills/ha, 2 kg Zn/ha, insect control using carbofuran (3G) at 16 and

20 kg/ha, and hand weeding at 20 and 30 d after transplanting.

Farmer's inputs were land preparation with 2 plowings and 1 planking in standing water, transplanting with 50-d-old seedlings, plant population of 125,000 hills/ha, fertilizer at 50-13 kg NP/ha, no Zn, no insect and weed control.

The contribution of plant density to the yield gap was 43-45% for IR6 and 55% for Basmati 370 (see figure). The contribution of fertilizer was 33-39.5% for IR6 and 27% for Basmati 370. Other test factors' contributions follow: land preparation for IR6, 22.6%; insect control (for Basmati 370), 18%; weed control, 10-17%; and seedling age (IR6), 9.7%. □

Effect of soil N on rice yield in Punjab

N.S. Dhillon, R.K. Gupta, and G. Dev. Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab, India

We conducted 15 experiments in farmers' fields using 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha as urea, replicated twice. Surface soil samples of Typic Ustochrepts (0-15 cm) collected before transplanting were loamy sand to loam in texture, alkaline (pH 7.4 to 8.8), nonsaline (EC 0.06 to 0.48 dS/m), and low to medium in organic C (0.14 to 0.68%). The mean and range of soil test

Contribution of test factors to yield gap. Punjab, Pakistan.

Table 1. Status of nitrogen in rice growing soils. Punjab, India.

Soil N fraction	N content (µg/g soil)	
	Range	Mean
Total N	392-952	643
Hydrolyzable N	233-699	468
Hydrolyzable amino acid N	60-168	106
Hydrolyzable hexosamine N	14-56	28
Hydrolyzable NH ₄ -N	42-140	94
Nonhydrolyzable N	112-309	220

Table 2. Relationships of soil N fractions with yield and N uptake by rice. Punjab, India.

Soil N fraction	Relative yield	Relative N uptake
Total N	0.54*	0.68**
Hydrolyzable N	0.52*	0.66**
Hydrolyzable amino acid N	0.43	0.60*
Hydrolyzable hexosamine N	0.61*	0.60*
Hydrolyzable NH ₄ -N	0.64**	0.72**
Nonhydrolyzable N	0.55*	0.67**

^a Significance at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

$$\text{Relative yield/relative uptake} = \frac{\text{Yield or uptake without N}}{\text{Maximum yield or uptake with N}} \times 100.$$